

two nodes. A robot capable of identifying the labels of nearby entities can localize itself uniquely in the graph. Additionally, by following a sequence of identifiable entities, the robot can navigate to any entity. In another scenario, which we refer to as *Non-Unique Isolated Entities*, some entities share the same label but are not in LoS of each other. This can lead to ambiguities where identical or similar sets of entities are observed from different positions. The most complex scenario is when there are no restrictions on the label's uniqueness. In this case, the robot could reach clusters of completely identical entities.

2) *Localization*: We define the robot's possible states as the set of nodes in the graph, and the entities observed from the robot's current position as its observations. For each node where the probability exceeds a certain threshold, we apply a Histogram Filter. The filter first expands the probability from a node to its neighbours via an average of the two probability values. Then, it updates the belief of the robot's location by comparing the observations to the expected entities at each node. While with *Unique Entities*, this localization technique is irrelevant, when considering *Non-Unique Isolated Entities*, it allows to solve the ambiguities as soon as a discriminating entity is observed.

3) *Mapping*: To generate the EGM, we follow a simple strategy: the robot navigates from one entity to another, stopping close to every entity and collecting a set of observations. These observations are collected in a table, and whenever there is a confirmation of LoS from both entities, it is added as part of the graph.

4) *Path Planning*: Given the graph, the path from the robot's current state to a goal entity is obtained via Dijkstra's algorithm applied to the graph. Then, the robot navigates the graph by moving from one entity to another.

5) *Control and obstacle avoidance*: In order to move the robot from one entity to another, we employ the Social Force Model (SFM) control, treating the target entity as an attractive force and surrounding obstacles as repulsive forces.

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

We designed a 2D map to test the EGM explained in Section II, consisting of a collection of objects and obstacles, as depicted in Figure 1a. From this, we generate the EGM, illustrated in Figure 1b. We model the robot as a unicycle with a fixed detection range. We set different goal entities and run the algorithm to reach them from unknown starting positions. The robot explores the environment until the localization estimate of the node on the EGM converges. Then, the path planning algorithm computes a feasible trajectory through the entries to reach the goal. The results are shown in Figure 2a, where the goal is the crate on the right, and in Figure 2b, where it reaches the shed on the top left. The final trajectory may not always be optimal. However, the combination of the trajectory as a list of target entities, coupled with FSM control, enables the robot to successfully reach the desired entity. A key advantage of this approach is its memory efficiency. The

map, which measures 53m by 40m, would typically require a high-resolution occupancy grid. Assuming a resolution of 4 cells per meter, the occupancy grid would result in a [160x214] matrix, with approximately 7310 occupied cells. In contrast, our entity-based approach, with an entity density of 0.0125 entities/m², generates a graph with just 26 nodes and 56 edges. By saving the two maps as Matlab files, the occupancy grid weighs 2143 bytes, while the graph weighs 1390 bytes. Another advantage is that computing an entity-based path is significantly faster than planning a detailed 2D trajectory using traditional methods like RRT* or A*. Additionally, because the robot is not constrained to a predefined trajectory, it doesn't require high-frequency state estimation, which reduces the overall computational burden.

Fig. 2: Robot trajectory towards the crate (left) and the shed (right), starting from different points.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we developed a framework that diverges from traditional robotics mapping and planning methods, which rely heavily on precise metric information, by adopting a more semantic-oriented approach. This shift enables more flexible and meaningful interactions with the environment by emphasizing entity-based representation rather than exact positioning. Additionally, it significantly reduces the overall memory requirements for map storage.

For future work, we plan to improve the entire online map generation. Additionally, we aim to deploy this framework on a real robot and evaluate its performance in real environments. Further exploration is needed to address ambiguities that arise from the more general case without restrictions on the uniqueness of entities.

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